

Firm Characteristics and Corporate Governance Mechanisms as Drivers of Corporate Social Responsibility Disclosure in Zimbabwe

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Abstract:

This study extends the literature on the determinants of voluntary disclosure of corporate social responsibility (CSR) in a sample of 61 annual reports from the Zimbabwe Stock Exchange for the year ended 31 December 2020. The purpose of the study is to determine why firms voluntarily disclose CSR and whether corporate governance mechanisms have an impact on firms' disclosure policy. An unweighted disclosure index consisting of 30 corporate social responsibility attributes was developed; using content analysis to determine the level of corporate social responsibility disclosure. The results show that corporate social responsibility disclosure is low,

with the most corporate social responsibility information disclosed being community involvement disclosure (40%), followed by environmental disclosure (30%), products and consumer information disclosure (29%), and human resources disclosure (28%). In addition, using multiple regression analysis and after accounting for size, leverage, profitability and industry, the findings indicate that board independence and board of directors' qualifications have a significant positive influence on corporate social responsibility disclosure whereas ownership concentration was found to be insignificant. With the exception of profitability, all other firm characteristics, leverage, firm size and industry sector were positive and significant in explaining the variation in corporate social responsibility disclosure. It appears that profitable firms are not motivated to increase corporate social responsibility disclosure. This may be consistent with the shareholder wealth maximization approach which renders corporate social responsibility disclosures as less important. Financial markets in Zimbabwe may not be sufficiently efficient in penalizing firms for incomplete corporate social responsibility disclosure and that regulators may need to mandate such disclosures if information asymmetry is to be reduced and market efficiency enhanced.

Keywords: *Corporate social responsibility, Corporate governance, Board independence, Board qualifications, Voluntary disclosure.*

Introduction

The economic activities of firms have an impact on the sustainability of the environment. This

impact is of interest to society as stakeholders expect firms to operate responsibly in a bid to be perceived as legitimate (Zimmerman & Zeit, 2002). Firms disclose their corporate social

responsibility (CSR) initiatives in their financial reports in order to illustrate the legitimacy of their operations (Giannarakis, 2014; Hasseldine, Salama, & Toms, 2005). These voluntary disclosures are aimed at reducing information asymmetry related to the firm's adaptability and survival strategy (Kerr, Janda, & Pitts, 2009) as well as in shaping corporate reputations (Teece, Pisano, & Shuen, 1997; Said, Yuserrie, & Hasnah, 2009). According to Fombrun, Gardberg, and Barnett (2000), corporate social responsibility voluntary disclosure (CSRVD) assists firms to build alliances with stakeholders, assists firms in enhancing reputational capital (Grant 1991; Roberts & Dowling, 2002), reduces the cost of capital (Jensen & Meckling, 1976; Déjean & Martinez, 2009) and generates sustained superior financial performance (Roberts & Dowling, 2002). An alternative view, put forward by Friedman (1970) suggests that firms have no obligation towards society, despite the fact that CSR has gained much importance in recent decades. Furthermore, Sternberg (1997) criticized the stakeholder approach to CSR arguing that the theory is fundamentally misguided and incapable of providing better performance, conduct or governance. To what extent are firms responsible and accountable to society and to the environment given the overriding objective of maximizing profits? Where firms adopt an overstretched CSR engagement approach it is likely to adversely influence profits (Steinmann, 2007). In addition, it is unlikely for consumers, through their buying patterns, to influence firms' policies towards CSR (Will *et al.*, 1988; Bauman, 2009). Alternatively, bearing in mind the fiduciary role of directors to shareholders, Sundaram and Inkpen (2004) suggest a re-evaluation of the governance structures of corporate boards and whether these may positively impact CSR disclosures as directors are expected to provide complete disclosures to shareholders.

Overall, CSRVD in developing and less developed countries in Africa remains low and unsatisfactory (Jere *et al.*, 2016); in Egypt, disclosures are merely descriptive (Rizk, Dixon, & Woodhead, 2008); in most Arab countries CSRVDs are low (Kamla, 2007). Higher

CSRVDs have been identified in developed economies (Chih, Chih, & Chen, 2010; Kapoor & Sandhu, 2010; Krasodomka, 2015; Li & Zhang, 2010; Giannarakis, 2014; Cuadrado-Ballesteros, Rodríguez-Ariza, & García-Sánchez, 2015; Medrado & Jackson, 2016; Nekhili, Nagatib, Chtioui, & Rebolledo, 2017; Sotorrio & Sanchez, 2017; Yin, 2017) and are attributed to larger and more efficient financial markets and stronger economic development, enforced legal systems and more effective corporate governance (CG) practices (Barakat, Pérez, & Ariza, 2015). Several studies focused on developing and emerging economies (Hackston & Milne, 1996; Gelb & Strawser, 2001; Ali, Frynas, & Mahmood, 2017; Laskar & Maji, 2017) whilst others were conducted in developed economies (Branco & Rodrigues, 2008; Reverte, 2009; Gamerschlag, Möller, & Verbeeten, 2011; Barakat *et al.*, 2015; Ali *et al.*, 2017).

Some studies from an international perspective examined CSRVD of firms in the same type of industry (Chih *et al.*, 2010; Li & Zhang, 2010; Medrado & Jackson, 2016; Laskar & Maji, 2017) in addition, the majority of studies from Zimbabwe examined CSR in different single industries or in different single sectors for instance, Menenji (2018) investigated the impact of CSR practices on employee motivation and performance in the telecommunications sector, Magaya & Nhavira (2016) studied CSR in the construction industry, Murombo (2016) studied CSR in the extractive sector, Dlamini & Mavengere (2019) investigated CSR disclosure and firm performance in the banking sector and established an insignificant negative relationship, Chanakira, M., & Masunda (2019) reviewed CSR engagement in the SMEs sector, Mlilo (2018) examined CSR and firm performance in the insurance industry whilst Makanyeza *et al.* (2018) examined dimensions of CSR and firm performance in all industries, however these dimensions were not linked to disclosure; Sibanda *et al.* (2021) investigated CSR strategies and business survival and concluded that different strategies are required for different industries, whilst Mathende & Nhapi (2017) undertook a study to conceptualisation and understand the determinants of CSR whilst

exploring the experiences of communities.

Prior studies indicate that three main methodologies are used by authors to research CSR and include information synthesis and analysis, survey and quantitative methods. In general, with the exception of Sifile, Susela, Mabvure, Chavunduka, and Dandira (2014) and Jere, Ndamba, and Mupambireyi (2016), who examined CSRVD and focused on corporate board failure and on legitimacy respectively, studies in Zimbabwe have concentrated more on the impact of CSR on firm performance, no study to date has been identified as modelling the determinants of CSR disclosure based on a positivist approach/quantitative methodology consistent with general disclosure studies which suggest that the most common form of disclosing CSR is through annual reports (Lindblom, 1983). Prior studies indicate that disclosure indices are generated by authors in order to measure the extent of CSR disclosures (Verbeeten, Gamerschlag, & Möller, 2016; Bayoud, Kavanagh, & Slaughter, 2012; Rahman, Zain, & Al-Haj, 2011). Giannarakis (2016) used as a proxy three sub-dimensions, namely, environmental, social and governance for the extent of CSR disclosure. This research examines the drivers of CSR's individual disclosure components consisting of community involvement (Gamerschlag *et al.*, 2010; Tagesson *et al.*, 2009), environmental disclosure (Gamerschlag *et al.*, 2010; Jennifer Ho and Taylor, 2007), products and consumer information (Branco and Rodrigues, 2008) and human resources (Tagesson *et al.*, 2009) within a context that includes all industries. Furthermore, the study introduces a new theoretical framework that combines the motivation for CSR activity, policies and procedures, the possession of CSR attributes and resources and the voluntary disclosure of CSR attributes. An additional contribution focuses on a new methodology that applies a positivist philosophy unlike the phenomenological approach applied in prior studies in Zimbabwe. In addition, the interaction of CG mechanisms, firm specific characteristics and CSR individual component disclosure practices is modelled in a manner not previously investigated within the Zimbabwean

literature.

Literature Review and Hypothesis Development

Literature Review

Literature suggests that legitimacy theory (Deegan, 2002; Patten & Crampton, 2004; Branco & Rodrigues, 2006; Reverte, 2009) stakeholder theory (Roberts, 1992; Donaldson & Preston, 1995; Branco & Rodrigues, 2008; Dyduch & Krasodomska, 2017), agency theory (Jensen & Meckling, 1976; Ben-Amar & McIlkenny, 2015) and signalling theory (Ross, 1977; Trueman, 1986; Morris, 1987; Shi, Kim, & Magnan, 2014), non-proprietary costs hypothesis (Dye, 1985; Dye, 1986; Prencipe, 2004), resource dependency theory (Pfeffer, 1972; Hillman, Canella, & Paetzold, 2000), shareholder wealth maximisation hypothesis (Jensen, 2002; Sundaram and Inkpen, 2004) and resource-based view of the firm and competitive advantage (Wernerfelt, 1984; Campbell, Craven, & Shrive, 2003; Branco & Rodrigues, 2006; O'Connor & Spangenberg, 2008) may provide the theoretical framework necessary to model CSRVD. The differentials in CSRVD may be attributed to the presence of firm-specific resources that are valuable, rare, inimitable and non-substitutable (VRIN). Under these conditions, signalling may be a viable option as proprietary costs may be limited (Barney, 1999; Bowman & Ambrosini, 2003). These theories are applied in developing the hypotheses that raise an expectation as to the influence of each independent variable in the variation of CSRVD. The inclusion of CG mechanisms is derived from the fiduciary role of directors to shareholders (Sundaram & Inkpen, 2004) in corporate boards and the ongoing modelling of CSR and CG in disclosure studies (Kolk & Pinkse, 2010; Khan, Muttakin, & Siddiqui, 2013; Elsakit & Worthington, 2014; Giannarakis, 2014; Ali *et al.*, 2017; Kuhnet *al.*, 2018; Pucheta-Martínez & Gallego-Álvarez, 2018; Lagasio & Cucari, 2019) in which disclosure is enhanced under good governance.

Literature has presented several drivers of CSR

disclosure covering financial characteristics, corporate governance characteristics (Haniffa and Cook, 2005) and firm-specific characteristics (Dyduch & Krasodomska, 2017; Charumathi & Ramesh, 2015; Sundaram & Inkpen, 2004). In order to develop the model and analyse the relationship between CSRVD and the independent variables, the following financial characteristics, profitability and leverage, corporate governance characteristics, ownership concentration, board of directors' qualifications and board independence and the following firm specific characteristics, firm size and industry sector are introduced. In order to

test the hypotheses and the following statistical methods are applied, correlation analysis and regression analysis (Jennifer Ho and Taylor, 2007; Tagesson et al., 2009; Gamerschlag *et al.*, 2010; Khan, 2010; Giannarakis, 2014; Rahman, Zain, & Al-Haj, 2011 and Branco and Rodrigues, 2008). In our analysis, values of dependent variables CSRVD are continuous and have a lower bound of zero in some cases as such both a linear regression model and a quantile regression are applied. Thus the analytical framework examines the interaction between CSR disclosure attributes and corporate governance.

Table 1. Analytical Framework

	High Level of CSR Best Practices	Low Level of CSR Best Practice
High Level of Corporate Governance Compliance	<u>Quadrant 1:</u> High Level of CSRVD Legitimacy theory, stakeholder theory, resource based view, signalling	<u>Quadrant 2:</u> Low Level of CSRVD Legitimacy theory, stakeholder theory, resource based view and signalling vs. agency theory and proprietary cost hypothesis
Low Level of Corporate Governance Compliance	<u>Quadrant 3:</u> Moderate to Low Level of CSRVD Legitimacy theory, stakeholder theory, resource based view and signalling vs. agency theory and proprietary cost hypothesis.	<u>Quadrant 4:</u> Very Low Level of CSRVD Agency theory and proprietary cost hypothesis.

Source: Authors

In quadrant 1, firms are motivated and have implemented and maintained CSR best practices and coupled with CG compliance, the expectation based on the resource based view of the firm and signalling theory, is that these firms will have the highest level of voluntary disclosure barring any proprietary costs that may limit such voluntary disclosure. In quadrant 2, firms have very little CSR to disclose; these firms may either not practice CSR or are in industries in which CSR may consist of insignificant reporting attributes. The presence of CG best practices may be rendered insignificant due to the absence of CSR practices. In quadrant 3, the low level of CG compliance enhances the presence of agency costs and renders the financial reporting process ineffective therefore reducing voluntary disclosure even in the presence of CSR best practice. Furthermore, due to the presence of agency costs, proprietary

costs may be higher rendering voluntary disclosure costly. Voluntary disclosures are therefore moderate to low. Firms in quadrant 4 have the lowest voluntary disclosures as CSR best practice is low and agency costs are high due to low CG compliance. These firms do not practice CSR and do not have an effective financial reporting process. Furthermore, proprietary costs are likely to be significant due to the lack of VRIN attributes in disclosures. Within each quadrant, firms with varying characteristics are likely to develop different CSR disclosure strategies. As such the varying degrees of firm size, profitability and leverage are likely to influence the level of voluntary disclosure. Furthermore, industry sector will have a dual impact based on the business model and the industry reporting frameworks.

Hypotheses Development

Profitability

Some studies argue that profitability does not appear to be a significant determinant of social responsibility disclosure (Domench, 2003; Brammer & Pavelin, 2006; Dlamini & Mavengere, 2019) whereas a few others, Prencipe (2004), Baroka *et al.* (2006), Wang and Sewon (2008), Kolsi (2012), Ali *et al.* (2017) and Elgergeni *et al.* (2018) found a positive and significant relationship with profitability. Neu, Warsame, and Pedwell (1998) applied a legitimacy theory framework in establishing that profitability is considered to be both positively and negatively related to CSRVD. The resource based view of the firm (Branco & Rodrigues, 2006; Wernerfelt, 1984) illustrates that the more profitable firms are more likely to possess the resources necessary for the development and maintenance of CSRVD based on the RBV and signalling frameworks (Ross, 1977; Morris, 1987). Consistent with prior studies, this study adopts an accounting measure for profitability, return on assets (ROA) as a measure of economic performance (Belkaoui & Karpik, 1989; Bewley & Li, 2000; Brammer & Pavelin, 2006; Branco & Rodrigues, 2008). This variable ROA is measured by the ratio of net income/total assets. Based on the RBV of the firm and signalling theory, the following hypothesis is thus tested:

H₁: CSRVD is positively associated with profitability.

Firm Size

Firm size is expected to be significant and positively associated with CSRVD since larger firms are more visible and hence attract more attention from the general public as well as from the media and government (Branco & Rodrigues, 2008; Khan, 2010; Rahman, Zain, & Al-Haj, 2011; Arora & Dharwadkar, 2011; Suttipun & Stanton, 2012). Larger firms are also geographically dispersed and may be more diversified across product markets, hence are susceptible to public scrutiny (Brammer & Pavelin, 2004). Company size can be measured using various methods such as market capitalisation, asset base, sales value or number

of employees (Branco & Rodrigues, 2008; Hackston & Milne, 1996), thus, the measure used in this study is the natural logarithm of total assets, as reported in the statement of financial position of the firm (Haniffa & Cooke, 2005). The following hypothesis is thus tested:

H₂: There is a positive significant relationship between firm size and CSRVD.

Industry Sector/Industry Affiliation

Industries associated with more environmental impacts or with much higher public visibility or which have less favourable public images tend to disclose more information regarding CSR as compared to those with less or no environmental impacts (Gelb & Strawser, 2001; Domench, 2003; Gamerschlag *et al.*, 2011). Industry sector/affiliation is measured as a dummy variable for different industry profiles using a dichotomous classification of industries between high-profile and low-profile industries (Patten, 1991; Roberts, 1992; Hackston & Milne, 1996). High-profile industries are those with consumer visibility, concentrated intense competition, or a high level of political risk as well as those in extractive industries, and these among others include automobile, petroleum, mining, chemicals, forest and paper, agriculture, transportation, tobacco, liquor, media and communication, airline, oil industries, engineering, technology, building and associated industries and printing and publishing (Patten, 1991; Roberts, 1992; Hackston & Milne, 1996). Those identified as low-profile industries include food, health, retail, tourism, banking and financial, insurance, property and pharmaceuticals and hotel (Roberts, 1992). Based on legitimacy theory consistent with Branco and Rodrigues (2008) high profile companies and in particular manufacturing companies may disclose more social, environmental, health and safety issues than companies belong to other sectors in order to avoid public pressure and additional regulations (Hackston & Milne, 1996; Tagesson, Blank, Broberg, & Collin, 2009). On the basis of such arguments, the study hypothesises that;

H₃: There is a positive relationship between industry sector/affiliation with CSRVD.

Leverage

Leverage has had mixed results based on prior studies (Branco & Rodrigues, 2008; Reverte, 2009; Dyduch & Krasodomska, 2017; Laskar & Maji 2017). Barnea and Rubin's (2010) research suggests a negative association between leverage and CSRVD. Roberts (1992) stated that the power of stakeholder groups such as creditors depends upon the degree to which a firm relies on debt financing. Highly leveraged firms are likely to be under financial constraint and may lack the financial flexibility to engage in CSR best practices. The research concludes based on an agency theory approach that high levels of leverage may lead to a reduction in CSRVD. Leverage may act as a disciplining mechanism on management and thus reduce agency costs; nevertheless, too much debt may result in an increase in the agency costs of debt due to the overinvestment and underinvestment problems (Jensen & Meckling, 1976; Myers, 1977; Jensen, 1986; Mao, 2003). Following previous studies (Belkaoui & Karpik, 1989; Brammer & Pavelin, 2006; Reverte, 2009), leverage is measured by the ratio of total debt/total assets. The following hypothesis is thus tested:

H₄: There is a negative significant relationship between leverage and CSRVD.

Ownership Concentration

Conflicts of interest between the owners of firms and management are more likely to occur in firms where ownership is more dispersed (Ullmann, 1985; Roberts, 1992; Reverte, 2009), where the power of shareholders is weak and where control by management is strong. Jensen and Meckling (1976) and Pucheta-Martínez and Gallego-Álvarez (2018) suggest that high ownership dispersion may lead to increased

disclosure in order to mitigate information asymmetry. However, concentrated ownership was also found to have a positive and significant impact on voluntary disclosures (Gelb & Strawser, 2001; Reverte, 2009; Garmarschlag *et al.*, 2010; Khan *et al.*, 2013; Ali *et al.*, 2017). The variable was measured from shareholder data obtained from the annual reports of the sample firms (Reverte, 2009; Gamerschlag *et al.*, 2011). Thus, the total ownership percentage of the top three and top five largest shareholders was used to measure ownership concentration consistent with Said *et al.* (2009) and Said *et al.* (2015) respectively, who reported a positive association between ownership concentration and CSRVD. The following hypothesis is thus tested:

H₅: There is a positive relationship between concentrated ownership and CSRVD.

Board of Directors' Qualifications

Directors' educational qualifications have been found to provide unique perspectives and innovative ideas to boards (Cox & Blake, 1991; Hilmer, 1998; Westphal & Milton, 2000) in addition, some studies have identified educational background is a significant factor in disclosure practices (Farook *et al.*, 2011; Haniffa and Cooke, 2002). Board of directors' educational qualifications also positively impacted voluntary disclosure practices (Gamerschlag, 2013). The value relevance of the disclosed human capital information was analysed by Gamerschlag (2013), whose results indicated that human capital information is value-relevant and that qualifications and competence issues are positively associated with firm value. Ruigrok, Peck, and Tacheva (2007), identified that qualifications are important for board diversity.

Table 2. Zimbabwe National Qualifications Framework

	Academic Level	Professional Level	Grading
1	PhD, DBA		10
2	Masters, post graduate diploma, post graduate certificate	Professional level 3	9
3	Honours under graduate degree	Professional level 2	8
4	General under graduate degree	Professional level 1	7
5	Advanced diploma	Technical level 2	6
6	Diploma	Technical level 2	5

7	Certificate	Artisans, assistant technicians, skilled worker	4
8	Advanced level	Skilled worker, specialised general worker	3
9	Ordinary level	Fundamental literacy and numeracy for general education	2
10	Primary level	Basic educational foundation	1

Source: Ministry of Higher and Tertiary Education, Science and Technology Development, Zimbabwe (2018)

Subramanian, Choi, Lee, and Hang (2016) reported a lack of association between educational level and innovation performance. However, Harjoto, Laksmana, and Lee (2015) and Katmon, Zuriyati, Norlia, Norwani, and Farooque (2017) reported a positive association between educational level diversity and CSR performance and disclosure, respectively. One study identified linking educational information with voluntary disclosure was conducted by Gamerschlag (2013) in which the study identified that human capital information voluntarily disclosed is value relevant by using a word-based content analysis on German companies' annual reports. An additional study by Ma, Zhang, Yin, and Wang (2019) illustrated that top managers' MBA educational background has a positive relationship with ENVDISC whereas top managers' legal educational background has a negative impact on ENVDISC. Therefore, both the depth and subject variation of different educational background of board members is important for strategic policies on improvement of CSRVD (Katmon *et al.*, 2017). Based on RBV theory and signalling theory, the signalling of qualifications may bridge the symmetric gap between the markets knowledge of a firm's resources and capabilities. Board qualifications are measured based on the Zimbabwe National Qualifications Framework (ZNQF) where qualifications are graded as illustrated in Table 2. The study hypothesis that:

H₆: There is a positive association between the level of CSRVD and board of directors' qualifications.

Board Independence

As asserted by Khan *et al.* (2013), the presence of independent directors in the board is considered to be a major CG mechanism. Similarly, Petra (2005) points that outside

independent directors play a pivotal role in strengthening the board by actively monitoring management activities thereby ensuring that investor's interests are well protected. Various studies such as Harjoto and Jo (2011) and Ortas *et al.* (2017) found that CSRVD is significantly correlated with board independence. Furthermore, Ooi, Amran, Yeap, and Jaaffar (2019) established that the extent of climate change disclosure increases with the presence of more independent directors. Board independence is measured by the ratio of independent directors /total number of directors in the board (Barako *et al.*, 2006; Cheng & Courtney, 2006; Rouf, 2011; Barakat *et al.*, 2015). To test whether board independence has an influence on CSR, the study developed the following hypothesis:

H₇: Ceteris paribus, there is a positive relationship between proportion of independent directors and the level of CSRVD.

Methodology

Several studies apply various research designs in determining CSRVD that include exploratory, descriptive and explanatory or narrative researches (Kothari, 2004). In their studies, Bichta (2003), Branco and Rodrigues (2006) and Jere *et al.* (2016) applied narrative researches in determine CSRVD. However, many other studies are both descriptive and explanatory (Brammer & Pavelin, 2006; Chih *et al.*, 2010; Li & Zhang, 2010; Giannarakis, 2014; Laskar & Maji, 2017); in addition, an exploratory research design was applied by Yin (2017). A few studies follow a phenomenological approach (Bichta, 2003; Yin, 2017). Nevertheless, most studies relating to CSRVD are from a positivist research philosophy (Branco & Rodrigues, 2008; Reverte,

2009; Charumathi & Ramesh, 2015; Medrado & Jackson, 2016) hence this study adopts a quantitative research approach.

The majority of studies on CSRVD applied content analysis (Krippendorff, 1980; Belkaoui & Karpik, 1989; Domench, 2003; Orlitzky, Schmidt, & Rynes, 2003; Kapoor & Sandhu, 2010; Gamerschlag *et al.*, 2011; Rouf, 2011). Other studies applied interviews, questionnaires and field researches such as Yin (2017). The analysis of CSRVD applied an equal-weighted

index (Barakat *et al.*, 2015; Branco & Rodrigues, 2008), that is, a scoring system which assigns a point for each CSRVD item pertaining to the categories under consideration. It follows that if a firm disclosed an item of information it received a score of 1 or otherwise it scored 0. The annual reports examined were for the year ended 31 December 2020. Thus, CSRVD in this study refers to voluntary disclosures in four categories as illustrated in Table 3, CSRVD by categories and attributes of voluntary disclosure.

Table 3. CSRVD Categories and Attributes of Voluntary Disclosure

A. ENVIRONMENTAL VOLUNTARY DISCLOSURE
Environmental policies or company concern for the environment Environmental management, systems and audit Pollution from business operations Pollution arising from use of products Discussion of specific environment laws and regulation Prevention or repair of damage to the environment Conservation of natural resources and recycling activities Sustainability Environmental aesthetics Conservation of energy in the conduct of business operations Energy efficiency of products
B. HUMAN RESOURCES VOLUNTARY DISCLOSURE
Employee Health and Safety Employment of minorities or women Employee training Employee assistance/benefits Employee remuneration Employee profiles Employee share purchase schemes Employee morale Industrial relations
C. PRODUCTS AND CONSUMERS VOLUNTARY DISCLOSURE
Product safety Product quality Disclosing of consumer safety practices Consumer complains/satisfaction Provision of disabled, aged, and difficult-to-reach consumers
D. COMMUNITY INVOLVEMENT VOLUNTARY DISCLOSURE
Charitable donations and activities Support for education Support for arts and culture Support for public health Sponsoring sporting or recreational projects

Source: Adapted from Barakat *et al.*, 2015; Branco and Rodrigues, 2008; Domench, 2003; Gray *et al.*, 1995.

The study mainly used secondary data which was publicly available in annual reports as in previous

voluntary disclosure studies (Hackston & Milne, 1996; Jere *et al.*, 2016). This was consistent with

other authors who applied this method in their previous studies in this field such as researches carried out by Hackston and Milne (1996), Branco and Rodrigues (2008), Reverte (2009), Kapoor and Sandhu (2010), Jere *et al.* (2016) and Kuhn *et al.* (2018). The Zimbabwe Stock Exchange (ZSE) listed firms formed the target population for the purpose of this study. There were 64 companies listed on the ZSE as at 05 September 2020. However, as at year end, 31 December 2020, three of the firms were suspended from trading hence the total population employed was 61 active firms and a sample of all the 61 firms was thus included in the study.

Table 4. Sample Summary by Sector

	Industry sector	Number of firms
1	Transport	1
2	Beverage	2
3	Tourism	2
4	Paper and Packaging	2
5	Agricultural	6
6	Retail	4
7	Banking and Financial	7
8	Mining	4
9	Engineering	3
10	Agri-Industrial	2
11	Food	4
12	Property	4
13	Printing and Publishing	1
14	Technology	1
15	Insurance	5
16	Building and Associated Industries	6
17	Pharmaceuticals and Chemicals	1
18	Industrial holdings	6
	TOTAL	61

Source: Authors - generated from surveyed sample of annual reports.

The population was selected because listed firms are mostly expected to report on corporate social responsibilities than unlisted firms (Branco & Rodrigues, 2008; Barakat *et al.*, 2015). The sample summary used is shown in Table 4. In order to test the hypothesis and analyse the relationship between CSRVD and the stated independent variables, the following regression analysis model was used:

$$CSRVD_i = \beta_0 + \beta_1 PROF + \beta_2 FSIZE + \beta_3 INDSECT + \beta_4 LEV + \beta_5 OWNCNTN + \beta_6 BODQ + \beta_7 BIND$$

Where,

CSRVD_i = Corporate Social Responsibility Voluntary disclosure score/index,

PROF = Profitability

LEV = Leverage

OWNSTRUCT = Ownership Concentration

BIND = Board Independence

BODQ = Board of directors' qualifications

FSIZE = Firm size

INDSECT = Industry sector

The research develops five models by varying the dependent variable (CSRVD_i) based on the nature of the voluntary disclosure attributes reported as follows:

Model I Environmental voluntary disclosure (ENVDISC_i)

Model II Human Resources voluntary disclosure (HRVDISC_i)

Model III Products and Consumer voluntary disclosure (PCVDISC_i)

Model IV Community Involvement voluntary disclosure (CIVDISC_i)

Model V CSRVD_i

In order to test the interaction of CSRVD_i with CG and the stated independent variables, PCVDISC_i is applied as a proxy for CSRVD_i. The research develops four models by varying Model III; the following models are generated where the dependent variable (PCVDISC_i) is regressed against the independent variables with the omission of one CG mechanism in each model. Both the Ordinary Least Squares Regression (OLS) and Quartile Regression (QREG) analysis are generated:

Model VI Leverage omitted (Lev)

Model VII Ownership concentration omitted (Ownstruct)

Model VIII Board qualifications omitted (BODQ)
 Model IX Board independence omitted (BIND)

of the dependent and independent variables included in our study. There is a higher variability in CSRVD across the ZSE listed firms as shown by a total CSR rating range of a minimum 0 to a maximum of 84. The total CSRVD mean of 27 out of 100 also suggest that CSRVD is still very low for the firms listed on ZSE. Variables which include BIND, FSIZE and LEV were transformed using logarithms for data normality in our regression.

Results and Findings

Descriptive Statistics

Table 5 below indicates the descriptive statistics

Table 5. Descriptive Statistics and Skewness and Kurtosis Tests for Data Normality

Variable	Obs	Mean	Std. Dev.	Min	Max	Skew Pr(Skewness)	Kurt Pr(Kurtosis)	chi2(2) adj.	Prob>chi2 Chi2(2)
ENVDISC	61	0.56	0.83	0.00	2.00	0.00	0.08	10.15	0.01
HRVDISC	61	0.52	0.74	0.00	2.00	0.00	0.57	8.62	0.01
PCVDISC	61	0.43	0.67	0.00	2.00	0.00	0.35	11.83	0.00
CIVDISC	61	0.92	0.74	0.00	2.00	0.66	0.00	9.96	0.01
TOTDISC	61	27.00	25.51	0.00	84.00	0.01	0.15	8.22	0.02
Bodq	61	7.72	1.08	6.00	10.00	0.07	0.21	4.83	0.09
Bind	61	74.92	11.01	50.00	88.89	0.01	0.86	5.89	0.05
Ownst	61	68.83	13.37	32.44	89.51	0.11	0.65	2.89	0.24
Fsize	61	7.83	0.66	6.09	9.32	0.73	0.23	1.61	0.45
Prof	61	1.94	10.95	-49.00	14.70	0.00	0.00	47.95	0.00
Lev	61	57.35	36.10	0.00	192.00	0.00	0.00	22.49	0.00
Indsect	61	0.59	0.50	0.00	1.00	0.21	.	.	.

Notes: TOTDISC: Total CSR voluntary disclosure; BODQ: Board of directors' qualifications; logBIND: logarithm of Board Independence; logFSIZE: logarithm of Firm Size; logLEV: logarithm of firm Leverage; PROF: Profitability; OWNST: Ownership concentration; INDSECT: Industry Sector

The descriptive, skewness and kurtosis data tests for normality were conducted and the results illustrated non-normality for some variables. These variables (; logBIND: logarithm of Board Independence; logFSIZE: logarithm of Firm Size; logLEV: logarithm of firm Leverage) were transformed and are presented in Table 5. Skewness and kurtosis test were applied in order to verify the normal distribution of the data. The results of the skewness indicate that for all variables skewness lies between +1.0 and -1.0 and are therefore within the parameters of ± 1.96 ; the kurtosis test results for all of the variables is within the range of ± 3 indicating normal distribution of data as results are below the mesokurtic threshold of 3. The probability of skewness which is within the range implies that skewness is asymptotically normally

distributed (p -value of skewness > 0.05). Conversely, Pr (Kurtosis) indicates that kurtosis is normally distributed (p -value of kurtosis > 0.05) and chi (2) is greater than 0.01 implying its significance at 1% level. Consequently, the null hypothesis cannot be rejected. Therefore, according to skewness and kurtosis tests for normality, residuals show normal distribution

Total disclosure is measured as a percentage and the descriptive statistics indicate that on average firms disclose 27% of all attributes and that the maximum disclosing firm reported 84% of attributes. The results indicate that although some firms have very little disclosure, other firms possess CSR attributes and do disclose these at high levels. The profitability and leverage of the firms is highly variable, ranging

from a minimum of -49% to 14.7% and 0% to 192% respectively. However, firm size is relatively stable as represented by a mean of 7.83 and a standard deviation of 0.66. Board qualifications, board independence, ownership structure and firm size appear to be normally distributed based on the tabled statistics above.

Correlation Analyses

All disclosure indices indicate high levels of collinearity amongst themselves as illustrated by Table 6 below. This is expected as firms with high levels of disclosure for one category of CSR will have relatively high levels for other categories of CSR too relative to other firms. Board qualifications indicates negative collinearity with board independence illustrating that the more independent boards are likely to be less qualified or that higher levels of qualifications on the board may breed reduced board independence; depending on the direction of causation. Although a board may be highly qualified, qualifications may be in a technical area, an area that may not lend itself to the promotion of good governance. The results of board qualifications indicate no other association with any other variables including the disclosure indices. Board independence on the other hand is associated with high levels of CSR disclosure for all categories but mostly relating to PCVDISC. Consistent with Khan *et al.* (2013), the presence of independent directors on the board enhances CSRVD. Ownership structure does not have an impact on any of the disclosure indices but is negatively associated with board independence consistent with the philosophy of dominant shareholder/manager concept under stewardship theory. The findings are consistent with Reverte (2009) who identified that this scenario arises when shareholders are strong and management is weak; Table 6 (Appendix) illustrates that concentrated ownership reduces board independence and therefore reduces CSRVD; indirectly and consistent with Pucheta-Martínez and Gallego-Álvarez (2018) who established that dispersed ownership leads to higher levels of CSRVD. This may be due to institutional investors influence and power or to shareholders lack of knowledge and lack of interest in CSR.

Consistent with Ali *et al.* (2017), firm size drives the CSRVD_i reporting agenda; larger firms may have the resources and know-how to possess CSR attributes and to signal their positive effect to markets. In addition, firm size has a negative correlation with industry sector illustrating that larger companies are mainly low profile firms.

The largest variation of an independent variable on CSRVD_i is attributed to the impact of profitability which is negative for ENVDISC, HRVDISC, PCVDISC and total disclosure (CSRVD_i) but positive for CIVDISC_i. It appears that profitable firms do not have independent boards, have concentrated ownership and are not leveraged. These firms focus exclusively on CIVDISC_i. Leverage on the other hand is associated with ENVDISC, PCVDISC and CSRVD. As a monitoring tool, debt levels may determine financiers' interest in contingent liabilities related to CSR and may demand more ENVDISC and PCVDISC. As such debt may be an important component in enhancing governance by reducing information asymmetry (Roberts, 1992). These leveraged firms appear to have more independent boards, perhaps due to the appointment of financiers representatives on these boards; in addition, leveraged firms are less profitable and have a more dispersed ownership structure indicating weaker shareholders and stronger managers. High profile firms are associated with higher levels of ENVDISC and PCVDISC. These firms are generally smaller and have a more dispersed ownership structure. Being in the public eye and of public interest these firms disclose information directly related to the public, environmental, product and customer (Gelb & Strawser, 2001; Domench, 2003) but neglect information on human resources.

Additional correlation tests were conducted and a Durbin-Watson score of 2.020 was reported. This score falls within the range of 1.5 to 2.5, correlations are therefore relatively normal as values under 1 or more than 3 would be cause for concern (Field, 2009). The Durbin-Watson score of 2.020 in this study therefore means that no autocorrelation problem exists hence the interpreted data results can be relied on. Multicollinearity diagnostics tests of all

explanatory variables were also conducted against the dependent variable. Multicollinearity inflates the variances of the parameter estimates and hence may lead to lack of statistical significance of individual predictor variables even though the overall model may be significant (Branco & Rodrigues, 2008). In this study, the presence of multicollinearity was tested based on the computation of the variance inflation factor (VIF). The general rule of thumb is that if any of the VIF values exceeds 5 or 10, it implies that the associated regression coefficients are poorly estimated because of multicollinearity (Montgomery, 2001). In this study, the VIF values ranges are 1.14 to 1.49 for all models thus, multicollinearity does not influence the interpretation of the regression

results.

Regression Analyses

The results of the OLS regression and Quartile regression analysis are reported in Tables 7 and 8 respectively. The results of the analyses reflect similar results with firm size, industry sector and board independence reflecting a positive and significant association with CSRVD_i. Profitability, leverage and board qualifications show a significant association with CSRVD_i in some of the models with profitability changing from positive to negative in some models. Ownership structure on the other hand, is insignificant in explaining the variation in CSRVD_i in all models.

Table 7. Ordinary Least Squares Regression (OLS) Models I, II, III, IV and V

	Model I	Model II	Model III	Model IV	Model V
	ENVDISC	HRVDISC	PCVDISC	CIVDISC	TOTDISC
Number of obs.	61	61	61	61	61
F(stat)	18.35***	4.85***	27.12***	13.91***	9.60***
R-squared	0.449	0.333	0.494	0.486	0.443
Prof	-0.005 (-0.48)	-0.017 (-1.51)	-0.123 (-2.16)**	0.019 (1.79)*	-0.278 (-0.96)
Fsize	0.368 (3.06)***	0.287 (1.94)*	0.446 (3.44)***	0.373 (3.90)***	17.476 (3.83)***
Indsect	0.885 (5.04)***	0.362 (1.99)*	0.504 (3.72)***	0.125 (0.68)	17.660 (3.37)***
Lev	0.005 (1.47)	-0.002 (-0.64)	0.003 (1.83)*	-0.003 (-0.69)	0.108 (1.02)
Ownst	0.000 (0.03)	0.002 (0.26)	0.006 (1.25)	0.003 (0.52)	0.192 (0.94)
Bodq	0.034 (0.39)	0.109 (1.37)	0.054 (1.06)	0.144 (2.45)**	1.923 (0.71)
Bind	0.017 (2.23)**	0.029 (4.48)***	0.013 (2.49)**	0.038 (6.15)***	0.655 (3.01)***
_cons	-4.670 (-3.41)***	-4.933 (-3.39)***	-5.366 (-3.82)***	-6.117 (-5.74)***	-203.050 (-4.47)***
Mean VIF	1.450	1.450	1.450	1.450	1.450
Swilk e (z) Prob>z	2.233**	2.233**	2.233**	2.233**	2.233**

Notes: TOTDISC: Total CSR voluntary disclosure; AUDCOM: Audit committee; logBIND: logarithm of Board Independence; logFSIZE: logarithm of Firm Size; logLEV: logarithm of firm Leverage; PROF: Profitability; OWNST: Ownership concentration; INDSECT: Industry Sector

Under the OLS regression Model III presents the most robust model with an F-statistic of 27.12 and significant at 1% confidence level and a R² of 0.494. Under the quartile regression

Model IV provides the highest R² value (0.253) with the most number of significant independent variables found in Model III. Although Models IV and V have higher R²

values, they present only one and two significant independent variables respectively, relative to the four presented under Model III. The study therefore identifies Model III for further investigation as regards the interaction of CG mechanisms in the development of Models VI to IX.

Thus the OLS model provides evidence that large high profile firms that are highly leveraged and that are managed by independent boards, and although performing poorly financially, will disclose the most number of attributes relating to products and consumers. Consistent with the hypothesized relationships, large and high

profile firms attract a significant amount of public interest and in particular to do with their products and consumers and may respond by signaling this information as a means of legitimizing their existence and operations in society. Highly leveraged firms attract additional monitoring from debt holders and may be required to provide more information in reducing asymmetric information. Board independence is likely to reduce agency costs and promote transparency and accountability. The significance of higher levels of PCVDISC may be driven by poor performance and may be a marketing strategy aimed at increasing market share and at a return to profitability.

Table 8. Quartile Regression (QREG) Models I, II, III, IV and V

	Model I	Model II	Model III	Model IV	Model V
	ENVDISC	HRVDISC	PCVDISC	CIVDISC	TOTDISC
Number Of Obs	61	61	61	61	61
Pseudo R2	0.163	0.122	0.172	0.253	0.241
Prof	-0.012 (-0.98)	-0.026 (-1.50)	-0.010 (-1.18)	0.022 (1.19)	-0.030 (-0.09)
Fsize	0.405 (2.69)**	0.248 (1.10)	0.324 (2.67)**	0.293 (1.11)	21.301 (4.69)***
Indsect	0.735 (3.44)***	0.282 (0.95)	0.509 (3.41)***	0.239 (0.73)	13.630 (2.43)**
Lev	0.004 (0.96)	-0.009 (-1.63)	0.003 (1.15)	-0.000 (-0.03)	0.136 (1.31)
Ownst	0.000 (0.00)	-0.001 (-0.09)	0.001 (0.19)	0.005 (0.45)	0.023 (0.11)
Bodq	0.186 (1.92)*	0.097 (0.76)	0.138 (1.94)*	0.102 (0.70)	1.380 (0.52)
Bind	0.024 (2.31)**	0.031 (2.23)**	0.016 (2.31)**	0.039 (2.64)**	0.416 (1.66)
_Cons	-6.533 (-3.81)***	-4.134 (-1.76)*	-5.025 (-4.08)***	-5.752 (-2.10)**	-200.841 (-4.28)***

Notes: TOTDISC: Total CSR voluntary disclosure; AUDCOM: Audit committee; logBIND: logarithm of Board Independence; logFSIZE: logarithm of Firm Size; logLEV: logarithm of firm Leverage; PROF: Profitability; OWNST: Ownership concentration; INDSECT: Industry Sector

Based on the analytical framework Table 1, overall results under the OLS regression analysis indicate that results (R^2 0.494) fall between quadrant 2 and quadrant 3 in which disclosures are moderate to low level and low level of CSRVD respectively. The theoretical framework includes emphasis on stakeholder theory and

legitimacy theory for management and institutional motivation respectively and the resource based view and signalling theory or resource based view and agency theory/non-proprietary cost hypothesis for the reporting of such information. The QREG analysis indicates that results (R^2 0.253) fall between quadrant 3

and quadrant 4 where voluntary disclosure is moderate to low level and very low level respectively; the more dominant theoretical perspectives in quadrant 4 being agency theory and proprietary cost hypothesis.

Nevertheless, the results indicate that there are large variations in disclosure practices between attributes within the same firms and between firms. It may therefore not be appropriate to generalise empirical findings on CSR as a whole but rather to examine attribute categories individually to establish management's motivation to disclose in particular areas. The research has established that the impact of control and CG variables of CSRVD_i is varied depending on the attributes included in the dependent variables, adding more complexity to the study on CSR drivers. The following discussion on the independent variables influence on CSRVD_i is analysed by examining on their varying impacts on Models I to V and the varying theoretical relationships that seem to raise an expectation in one area of CSRVD_i but are found insignificant in other areas requiring additional investigation of established theoretical perspectives in the CSR literature.

Profitability

Profitability is significant and negative in Model III of the OLS regression and significant and positive in Model IV of the OLS regression but insignificant in all other models including those of the QREG analysis. The results indicate that profitability reduces CSRVD_i with respect to PCVDISC but enhances CSRVD_i with respect to CIVDISC. The results are consistent with Dyduch and Krasodomska (2017) who showed a positive relation with profitability concerning social voluntary disclosure. Thus the more profitable firms will focus on CIVDISC and those non-performing firms, on PCVDISC attributes, as pointed out by Barakat *et al.* (2015), PCVDISC is driven by the firms' interest to maintain and improve sales. Profitability of the firm indicated a negative relation with CSRVD and this is consistent with Branco and Rodrigues (2008), Charumathi and Ramesh (2015) and Dlamini & Mavengere (2019). This can be attributed to the harsh economic environment

experienced in Zimbabwe during the period under study as most firms were incapacitated due to adverse macroeconomic fundamentals. However, as literature suggest, this may imply that in firms with less economic resources, focus is much more directed to other activities that promote the firm's earnings rather than the production of environmental and social voluntary disclosures (Hackston & Milne, 1996; Pirsch, Gupta, & Grau, 2007). The results are therefore inconclusive and are consistent with the literature which provides mixed results on whether profitability is a significant corporate CSRVD determinant (Neu *et al.*, 1998; Domench, 2003; Brammer & Pavelin, 2006; Ali *et al.*, 2017; Elgergeni *et al.*, 2018). Whereas consistent with the RBV of the firm, signalling theory (Ross, 1977; Morris, 1987) and non-proprietary cost hypothesis (Dye, 1985; Dye, 1986; Prencipe, 2004), firms will signal positive information and will suppress the disclosure of negative information depending on the impact on future cash flows.

Firm size

Firm size is positive and significant for all models with the exception of Model II (HRVDISC) and Model IV (CIVDISC) of the QREG analysis. In these models only one independent variable, board independence, is significant in explaining the variation in HRVDISC_i. The low levels of human resource attributes disclosed may be attributed to lack of board independence and the inability of other CG mechanisms to impact on this reporting. Being a large firm or a small firm does not influence HRVDISC_i, as there may be other drivers of issues to do with human resources, in particular, confidentiality and the non-proprietary cost hypothesis perspective. Community involvement disclosures have been established to be industry wide, irrespective of size or sector as this has been the general focus of companies on the ZSE. Nevertheless, the majority of studies indicate a significant positive association with CSRVD_i as illustrated by Branco and Rodrigues (2008) who concluded that large firms are seen to be disclosing more information as compared to smaller firms. This is largely due legitimacy and the avoidance of adverse

reactions if not socially conscious. Diversification that is found in larger firms may also lead to added public scrutiny (Brammer & Pavelin, 2004). Thus firm size can be considered to have an impact on CSRVD_i.

Industry sector

Models I, III and V report a positive and significant association of industry sector with CSRVD_i in the OLS and QREG analyses. In Model II, where the dependent variable is HRVDISC_i, industry sector is positive and significant only in the OLS analysis and in Model IV, where the dependent variable is CIVDISC_i, industry is insignificant in both the OLS and QREG analyses. Whereas the majority of models report a positive and significant relationship with CSRVD_i consistent with the RBV of the firm and signalling theory, human resources disclosures are limited consistent with non-proprietary cost hypothesis and this trend of non-disclosure is not industry specific. Community involvement disclosures are not influenced by industry affiliation but are driven by firm size and board independence. Furthermore, as community involvement being mainly, charitable donations and activities and support for education, can be conducted by firms in any industry, resources (firm size) and authorisation/motivation (board independence) become the key factors. Nevertheless, based on the majority of the models, it appears that high profile firms do attract public interest and that they do respond by signalling specific CSR attributes and suppressing the disclosure of other CSR attributes. Other factors may influence the disclosure of human resource disclosures in particular. The results are consistent with the findings of Gelb and Strawser (2001) and Domench (2003).

Leverage

The regression results indicate that leverage is insignificant in all models with the exception of Model III of the OLS analysis, in which the dependent variable is products and consumers PCVDISC_i. In addition, although other models are insignificant, the direction of the relationships between leverage and CSRVD_i varies from positive to negative, indicating that

debt may enhance or limit CSRVD_i dependent on the CSR attributes being reported. The significance of the results of Model III in the OLS analysis indicates a positive association between PCVDISC_i and leverage that may be attributed to additional monitoring by debt holders. Firms may respond by reducing information symmetry in particular with products and customers for the benefit debt holders, concerned with sales and marketing forecasts. Nevertheless, given the insignificance of the majority of the results of models, the evidence suggests that the impact of leverage on CSRVD_i is inconclusive consistent with Branco and Rodrigues (2008) who investigated the relationship between leverage and CSRVD. In addition, whilst Dyduch and Krasodomska (2017) identified a negative relation with leverage concerning social voluntary disclosure, Purushothaman (2000) and Charumathi and Ramesh (2015) established that firm leverage showed a positive association with CSRVD.

Ownership Structure

Ownership structure is not significant in any of the models in the OLS or QREG analyses. Whether firms have a concentrated or dispersed ownership structure, ownership structure does not have an impact of CSRVD_i. The results conflict with those of Pucheta-Martínez and Gallego-Álvarez (2018) who suggest that high ownership dispersion may lead to increased disclosure of environmental issues. In addition, Li and Zhang (2016) found a positive association to CSRVD for non-state owned firms in China and a negative relation to CSRVD for state-owned firms. The negative relation was insinuated to be due to political interference in that country. Thus although ownership structure has been found to influence CSR disclosure in the literature, this study finds the relationship to be insignificant. It appears that managers may be strong and shareholders weak, as board independence appears to be the more significant explanatory variable for the variation in CSRVD_i.

Board of Directors' Qualifications

The results for board qualifications vary from model to model with Model IV (CIVDISC_i) of

the OLS analysis and Models I (ENVDISC_i) and III (PCVDISC_i) of the QREG analyses reporting significant and positive results on the association with CSRVD_i (Harjoto *et al.*, 2015; Katmon *et al.*, 2017). All other models presented insignificant results with changing signs. Thus board qualifications have a different impact on different CSR component disclosures. Nevertheless, although the results may be conflicting between CSR component disclosures, board qualifications may be significant in explaining the variation in CSRVD_i consistent with Gamerschlag (2013), whose results indicated that human capital information is value-relevant and that qualifications and competence issues are positively associated with firm value. A further study by Darmadi (2013), established that the educational qualifications of board members and the CEO matter in explaining either ROA or Tobin's Q.

Board Independence

Board independence is positive and significant for all models in the OLS and QREG analyses with the exception of Model V (CSRVD_i) of the QREG analysis. In this Model V of the OLS analysis, only firm size and industry are significant in explaining the variation in CSRVD_i and may be the key elements with respect to access to resources; whereas industry sector may be significant in determining possession of CSR attributes. Thus board independence is the dominant CG mechanism that promotes CSRVD_i. Harjoto and Jo (2011) found that CSRVD is significantly correlated with board independence and Ooi *et al.*, (2019) established that the extent of climate change disclosure increases with the presence of more female and independent directors. Consistent with agency theory and the separation of ownership and control, management require the monitoring and supervisory role of non-executive directors if agency costs are to be minimised. Furthermore, as board independence impacts

board sub-committees and the decisions made, the board's independence has a wide reach across firm operations including nominations, remuneration, audit, operations, risk and strategy.

Regression Analysis: Interaction between CSR and CG Mechanisms

In order to investigate the interaction between CSR and CG mechanisms, the research developed four models as presented in Tables 9 and 10 where the dependent variable (PCVDISC_i) is regressed against the independent variables with the omission of one CG mechanism in each model. Both the OLS and QREG analysis are generated. Model III is identified as the most robust model based on the nature of CSR attributes disclosed, the model's *F-statistics* and *R²* result. A comparative analysis between the OLS and QREG analyses indicates that control variables are significant throughout all models under the OLS analysis; profitability illustrates a negative association whilst firm size and industry sector exhibit a positive association. The QREG analysis presents varying results on the control variables. In general, consistent with the OLS model, firm size and industry are positive and significant in explaining the variation in PCVDISC_i, with the exception of Model IX which presents unique results. As expected, the control variable (firm size) resulted in a positive relationship with CSRVD. This is consistent with other studies by Branco and Rodrigues (2008), Reverte (2009), Li and Zhang (2010) and Gamerschlag *et al.* (2011). Literature review illustrates that CSRVD is related to corporate size, as large firms are seen to disclose more information as compared to smaller firms (Branco & Rodrigues, 2008). This is due to higher visibility to and scrutiny by various stakeholder groups. Larger firms are also geographically dispersed and more diversified across product markets, hence are susceptible to public scrutiny (Brammer & Pavelin, 2004).

Table 9. Ordinary Least Squares Regression (OLS) Models I, II, III, IV and V (PCVDISCi)

	Model III	Model VI	Model VII	Model VIII	Model IX
	PCVDISC	PCVDISC	PCVDISC	PCVDISC	PCVDISC
Number Of Obs	61	61	61	61	61
F(Stat)	27.12***	26.73***	59.74***	51.00***	38.08***
R-Squared	0.494	0.475	0.482	0.488	0.455
Prof	-0.013 (-2.16)**	-0.020 (-4.19)***	-0.012 (-2.14)**	-0.013 (-2.39)**	-0.015 (-2.40)**
Fsize	0.446 (3.44)***	0.449 (3.99)***	0.437 (3.36)***	0.466 (3.66)***	0.469 (3.27)***
Indsect	0.504 (3.72)***	0.463 (3.33)***	0.491 (3.59)***	0.490 (3.69)***	0.445 (3.34)***
Lev	0.003 (1.83)*		0.003 (1.62)	0.003 (1.75)*	0.004 (1.91)*
Ownst	0.006 (1.25)	0.005 (1.08)		0.006 (1.22)	0.004 (0.84)
Bodq	0.054 (1.06)	0.049 (0.92)	0.055 (1.10)		0.021 (0.41)
Bind	0.013 (2.49)**	0.014 (2.72)***	0.012 (2.34)**	0.012 (2.30)**	
_Cons	-5.366 (-3.82)***	-0.540 (-3.86)***	-4.777 (-3.78)***	-4.982 (-3.59)***	-4.140 (-3.57)***
Mean Vif	1.450	1.140	1.490	1.480	1.460
Swilk E (Z) Prob>Z		2.233**	2.233**	2.233**	2.233**

Notes: TOTDISC: Total CSR voluntary disclosure; AUDCOM: Audit committee; logBIND: logarithm of Board Independence; logFSIZE: logarithm of Firm Size; logLEV: logarithm of firm Leverage; PROF: Profitability; OWNST: Ownership concentration; INDSECT: Industry Sector

Industry affiliation indicated a positive relation, which is consistent with Reverte (2009) and Gamerschlag *et al.* (2011). Clarke and Gibson-Sweet (1999) also reiterated that firms affiliated in industry sectors associated with larger potential environmental impact (high-profile industries) such as mining industry are more likely to provide information pertaining to the environment and firms in industries with high visibility among final consumers are more likely to consider essential issues of community involvement thereby disclosing information pertaining to such involvement.

Profitability although significant and negative in all models of the OLS analysis is only significant and negative in Model VI of the QREG analysis in which leverage has been omitted from the analysis. Thus, in the absence of the additional

monitoring effect of debt holders and the disciplining effect of debt repayments, loss making firms voluntarily disclose more CSRVD_i (product and consumer information). This may be attributed to the agency costs of debt which increase as a result of the high levels of debt associated with ZSE listed firms. At higher levels of leverage, debt does not mitigate the agency costs of separation of ownership and control but rather increases agency costs under the overinvestment and underinvestment problems (Jensen & Meckling, 1976; Myers, 1977; Jensen, 1986; Mao, 2003). The unique results presented in Model IX of the QREG analysis indicate that board independence is essential for all variations of the models presented as the absence of board independence in this model, renders all independent variables insignificant in explaining the variation in CSRVD_i.

Table 10. Quartile Regression (QREG) Models I, II, III, IV and V (PCVDISC_i)

	Model III	Model VI	Model VII	Model VIII	Model IX
CSRVD _i	PCVDISC	PCVDISC	PCVDISC	PCVDISC	PCVDISC
Number Of Obs	61	61	61	61	61
Pseudo R2	0.172	0.140	0.171	0.146	0.101
Prof	-0.010 (-1.18)	-0.019 (-2.90)***	-0.010 (-1.66)	-0.008 (-0.66)	-0.016 (-0.83)
Fsize	0.324 (2.67)**	0.305 (2.45)**	0.329 (4.12)***	0.379 (2.21)**	0.306 (1.02)
Indsect	0.509 (3.41)***	0.480 (2.85)***	0.514 (5.08)***	0.402 (1.75)*	0.307 (0.83)
Lev	0.003 (1.15)		0.003 (1.47)	0.005 (1.14)	0.005 (0.74)
Ownst	0.001 (0.19)	0.001 (0.25)		0.006 (0.77)	-0.002 (-0.12)
Bodq	0.138 (1.94)*	0.133 (1.89)*	0.149 (3.36)***		-0.020 (0.12)
Bind	0.016 (2.31)**	0.016 (2.21)**	0.017 (3.62)***	0.015 (1.51)	
_Cons	-5.025 (-4.08)***	-4.641 (-3.44)***	-5.040 (-6.91)***	-4.685 (-2.76)***	-2.671 (-0.98)

Notes: TOTDISC: Total CSR voluntary disclosure; AUDCOM: Audit committee; logBIND: logarithm of Board Independence; logFSIZE: logarithm of Firm Size; logLEV: logarithm of firm Leverage; PROF: Profitability; OWNST: Ownership concentration; INDSECT: Industry Sector

Under the OLS analysis in Model VII leverage becomes insignificant in the absence of ownership structure in explaining the variation in PCVDISC_i. Thus debt holders will positively influence CSRVD_i when our model holds ownership structure constant; in other words, PCVDISC_i is enhanced by debt holders only through the positive support of shareholders. In the absence of active shareholders, debt holders calls for additional information on PCVDISC_i, fall on deaf ears. No other changes take place in the model as a result of dropping ownership concentration.

In Model VIII, the research drops board of directors' qualifications form Model III. The OLS analysis reports no changes and the QREG analysis reports a decrease in the significance of the association between industry sector and PCVDISC_i. Thus the presence of a highly qualified board of directors differentiates the extent of PCVDISC practices by encouraging high profile firms to provide markets with appropriate and relevant information consistent with their CSR activities. In addition, the QREG

model illustrates that in the absence of board qualifications, board independence becomes insignificant as an explanatory factor. This indicates that unqualified boards of directors cannot be independent with respect to PCVDISC_i. Furthermore, the unique results of Model IX indicate that without board independence no other CG mechanisms or control variables have an impact on PCVDISC_i under the QREG model. As such, board independence and board qualifications indirectly, have a significant impact on CSRVD_i.

Conclusion and Recommendations

Overall, CIVDISC (40%) scored highest, seconded by ENVDISC (30%), followed by PCVDISC (29%) and lastly, HRVDISC (28%). Within community involvement, the two most disclosed attributes are charitable donations and activities with 61.76% and attributes relating to provision of disabled, aged and difficult to reach consumers 52.94%. More profitable firms focus on community involvement disclosure and those

non-performing firms, on products and consumer disclosure attributes. In general, profitable market leaders signal positive information and loss making followers suppress the disclosure of negative information. The analytical framework Table 1 provides the theoretical model applied to different quadrants ranking CSRVD_i. Under the OLS regression analysis, determinants of CSRVD_i provide an explanatory factor of R^2 0.494 which falls between quadrant 2 and quadrant 3. The QREG analysis indicates that the explanatory factor R^2 is 0.253 and therefore ranked between quadrants 3 and 4. The theoretical framework illustrates that the dominant philosophies may be derived mainly from quadrant 4, agency theory and proprietary cost hypothesis due to the low level of CSR attributes disclosed. Furthermore, the low R^2 -factors in the models indicate the existence of other factors that may be important in explaining the variation in CSRVD_i. For instance, the variation in industry sector does not appear to have an impact on community involvement disclosures which have been established to be industry wide, irrespective of size or sector. Under community involvement, the beverage sector disclosed the highest number of attributes (100%) whilst the least was disclosed by the pharmaceutical and chemical sector (0%). The most attributes presented under ENVDISC pertain to the mining sector (90.91%) and the least disclosures are found in the pharmaceutical and chemical sector at 0%. Thus various firms will fall into different quadrants for different attributes and will be motivated by different factors, internal and external dependent to a large extent on board independence, firm size and industry sector. The interaction of CG mechanisms and the control variables yield new findings on the potential moderating effects of leverage and board of directors' qualifications.

With respect to leverage, in the absence of the additional monitoring effect of debt holders and the disciplining effect of debt repayments, loss making firms voluntarily disclose more product and consumer information. This behaviour may be associated with the agency costs of debt. However, large high profile firms that are highly

leveraged and that are managed by independent boards, and although performing poorly financially, will disclose the most number of attributes relating to products and consumers. As expected, high profile firms are associated with higher levels of environmental and product and customer attributes. These firms are generally smaller and have a more dispersed ownership structure however they neglect to disclose information on human resources. Nevertheless, product and consumer disclosures are enhanced by debt holders only through the positive support of shareholders. In the absence of active shareholders, debt holders' call for additional information on these disclosures falls on deaf ears. Within HRVDISC, the two areas of least voluntary disclosure comprise attributes regarding employee remuneration 0% and employment of minorities or women 6%. Although firm size was found to be generally positive and significant, being a large or a small firm does not influence human resources disclosures, as there may be other drivers of the reporting of these attributes, in particular, confidentiality and the non-proprietary cost hypothesis perspective.

Leveraged firms appear to have more independent boards, perhaps due to the appointment of financiers representatives on these boards; in addition, leveraged firms are less profitable and have a more dispersed ownership structure indicating weaker shareholders and stronger managers. Highly leveraged firms attract additional monitoring from debt holders and may be required to provide more information in reducing asymmetric information. At higher levels of leverage, debt however does not mitigate the agency costs of separation of ownership and control but rather increases agency costs under the overinvestment and underinvestment problems. This could be attributable to the fact that 50% of the sampled firms are highly leveraged with more than 50% debt financing, hence a closer monitoring by the providers of finance leading to the firms disclosing more of CSR information in an attempt to reduce agency costs and consequently the cost of capital. It is not surprising that ownership structure has been found to be

insignificant in influence CSR disclosure, it appears that managers may be strong and shareholders weak, perhaps due to the presence of significant leverage in these firms.

The presence of a highly qualified board of directors differentiates the extent of PCVDISC practices by encouraging high profile firms to provide markets with appropriate and relevant information consistent with their CSR activities. However, in the absence of board qualifications, board independence becomes insignificant as an explanatory factor. This indicates that unqualified boards of directors cannot be independent with respect to PCVDISC; furthermore, without board independence no other CG mechanisms or control variables has an impact on PCVDISC. All sampled firms comprised of a more than 50% proportion of non-executive directors over the total directors of the firm, meaning a diverse and skilled and more independent board of directors is sensitive to, or brings positive contribution in terms of improvement on CSR disclosure policy.

Future researches in this area can include additional independent variables such as foreign ownership and government intervention, etc., that may affect CSRVD so that more varied research results are obtained. The models indicate that there are likely to be additional drivers for CSRVD; not included in this study. In addition, alternative theoretical perspectives including social and political theory may be explored. Lastly, a much larger sample can be employed so as to establish a more broad analysis of CSRVD by firms listed on the Zimbabwe Stock Exchange and perhaps investigated on a longitudinal basis.

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Appendix

Table 6. Correlation Analysis (Pearson \ Spearman's Rho)

	ENVDISC	HRVDISC	PCVDISC	CIVDISC	TOTDISC	Bodq	Bind	Ownst	Fsize	Prof	Lev	Indsect
ENVDISC	1.000	0.608	0.894	0.400	0.815	0.064	0.212	-0.078	0.231	-0.148	0.288	0.375
		***	***	***	***	0.622	0.101	0.549	*	0.256	**	***
HRVDISC	0.654	1.000	0.619	0.415	0.647	0.145	0.470	-0.088	0.234	-0.457	0.170	0.124
	***		***	***	***	0.265	***	0.500	*	***	0.191	0.341
PCVDISC	0.828	0.614	1.000	0.360	0.807	0.132	0.252	-0.033	0.276	-0.212	0.307	0.275
	***	***		***	***	0.309	*	0.803	**	0.101	**	**
CIVDISC	0.350	0.414	0.342	1.000	0.531	0.145	0.398	-0.009	0.391	0.176	0.028	-0.135
	***	***	***		***	0.265	***	0.947	***	0.175	0.828	0.301
TOTDISC	0.886	0.788	0.893	0.478	1.000	0.066	0.259	0.057	0.360	-0.066	0.186	0.132
	***	***	***	***		0.614	**	0.666	***	0.613	0.151	0.311
Bodq	-0.010	0.081	0.075	0.159	0.065	1.000	-0.122	0.025	0.143	0.011	0.005	-0.114
	0.940	0.534	0.568	0.221	0.621		0.348	0.852	0.270	0.933	0.968	0.382
Bind	0.234	0.406	0.264	0.442	0.310	-0.221	1.000	-0.193	0.188	-0.216	0.199	-0.200
	*	***	**	***	**	*		0.135	0.147	*	0.124	0.123
Ownst	-0.172	-0.125	-0.091	-0.012	-0.094	0.048	-0.233	1.000	-0.102	0.101	-0.163	0.015
	0.184	0.338	0.486	0.927	0.474	0.713	*		0.432	0.437	0.210	0.908
Fsize	0.276	0.255	0.437	0.392	0.457	0.184	0.140	-0.127	1.000	0.149	0.162	-0.216
	**	**	***	***	***	0.155	0.281	0.330		0.253	0.212	*
Prof	-0.339	-0.286	-0.400	0.255	-0.303	0.045	-0.214	0.224	0.003	1.000	-0.261	-0.010
	***	**	***	**	**	0.730	*	*	0.980		**	0.942
Lev	0.350	0.196	0.423	-0.100	0.360	-0.035	0.278	-0.270	0.266	-0.659	1.000	-0.212
	***	0.131	***	0.443	***	0.790	**	**	**	***		0.101
Indsect	0.404	0.141	0.234	-0.14	0.182	-0.092	-0.182	-0.021	-0.221	-0.147	-0.116	1.000
	***	0.279	*	0.29	0.160	0.480	0.160	*	*	0.259	0.372	